

Bifurcation and Topology of Equilibrium Sets

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Abstract. The normal forms and invariants of control systems with a single parameter are found. Then, bifurcations of equilibrium sets are classified.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we study bifurcation problems of nonlinear control systems with a single input and a single parameter. The following nonlinear system with parameter μ is considered

$$\dot{\xi} = f(\xi, \mu) + g(\xi, \mu)v. \quad (1)$$

The variable $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state, $v \in \mathbb{R}$ is the input variable and the parameter is $\mu \in \mathbb{R}$. The vector fields $f(\xi, \mu)$ and $g(\xi, \mu)$ are assumed to be C^k for some sufficiently large k . The system has a single input v and a single parameter μ . Our attention is focused on local bifurcation near the origin $(\xi, \mu) = (0, 0)$. Assume,

$$f(0, 0) = 0, \quad g(0, 0) \neq 0,$$

The equilibrium set E is defined to be

$$E = \{(x, \mu) | \exists v_0, f(x, \mu) + g(x, \mu)v_0 = 0\}. \quad (2)$$

The linearization of the system at the origin is (A, B)

$$A = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(0, 0), \quad B = g(0, 0).$$

The system is called linearly controllable if (A, B) is a controllable pair. As we know, system (1) can have infinite many equilibrium points. The topology of the set of equilibrium points can be changed as the parameter μ is varied. The goal of this paper is to classify the equilibrium sets according to the topology of the set of equilibrium points for fixed values of μ . It is found that the topology of equilibrium set can be different for values of μ near an uncontrollable point. Therefore, we assume the following condition throughout this paper.

Assumption:

$$\text{rank}([B \ AB \ A^2B \ \dots \ A^{n-1}B]) = n - 1. \quad (3)$$

To classify the equilibrium set and its bifurcation, it is necessary to introduce normal forms and transformations.

For systems with parameters, a transformation consists of a change of coordinates and a feedback. Both can be parameter related. More specifically, a transformation is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \phi(\xi, \mu) \\ u &= \alpha(\xi, \mu) + \beta(\xi, \mu)v \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

in which $\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}(0, 0)$ is nonsingular and $\beta(0, 0) \neq 0$. If a transformation is applied to (1), denote the equilibrium set of the resulting system by \bar{E} . Then, in a neighborhood of $(\xi, \mu) = (0, 0)$, a point (ξ, μ) is in E if and only if $(x, \mu) = (\phi(\xi, \mu), \mu)$ is in \bar{E} . Therefore, in the sense of diffeomorphism, the transformation (4) does not change the equilibrium set E (locally). Furthermore, the change of coordinates and feedback (4) does not change the properties of our interest such as controllability (of linearization) or stabilizability.

In § 2, we simplify nonlinear control systems by the transformations of form (4). A set of quadratic invariants are found which plays the key role in the study of the bifurcations near a critical point. In § 3, the parametrizations of equilibrium sets are discussed for systems with different normal forms.

2. NORMAL FORMS AND INVARIANTS

The first step of finding normal forms is to simplify the linear part. Since the controllability index of (A, B) is $n - 1$, there exists a linear change of coordinates and feedback independent of μ transforming the system (1) into

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \lambda z + \gamma\mu + O(z, x, \mu, u)^2 \\ \dot{x} &= A_2x + \Gamma\mu + B_2u + O(z, x, \mu, u)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\Gamma = [\gamma_1 \ \gamma_2 \ \dots \ \gamma_{n-1}]^T$, $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n-1}$ and $z \in \mathbb{R}$. The pair (A_2, B_2) is in $n - 1$ dimensional Brunovsky form. To further simplify the linearization of the system, consider another change of coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x}_1 &= x_1, & \bar{x}_2 &= x_2 + \gamma_1\mu, & \dots, \\ \bar{x}_n &= x_n + \gamma_{n-1}\mu, & \bar{u} &= u + \gamma_n\mu, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

which transforms system (5) into (7). For the reason of simplicity, we still use (z, x) and u to represent the state variables and control input for the new system.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \lambda z + \gamma \mu + O(z, x, \mu, u)^2 \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + O(z, x, \mu, u)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

If $\lambda \neq 0$, the equation for z can be simplified by $\bar{z} = z + \frac{\gamma}{\lambda} \mu$. In the resulting system, the equation for \bar{z} is

$$\dot{\bar{z}} = \lambda \bar{z} + O(\bar{z}, x, \mu, u)^3.$$

If $\lambda = 0$ and $\gamma \neq 0$, the change of coordinate $\bar{z} = \frac{1}{\gamma} z$ transforms the equation for z into

$$\dot{\bar{z}} = \mu + O(\bar{z}, x, \mu, u)^2.$$

The normal forms for the linear part of (1) are summarized in the following lemma.

Lemma 1 *Given a system (1) satisfying assumption (3). There exists a linear change of coordinates and feedback which transforms (1) into one of the following forms $\lambda \neq 0$*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \lambda z + f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + g_1^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + f_2^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + g_2^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u + \dots; \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$\lambda = 0$, *Jordan form*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \mu + f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + g_1^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + f_2^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + g_2^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u + \dots; \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$\lambda = 0$, *diagonal form*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + g_1^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + f_2^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + g_2^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u + \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In the normal form, λ is the uncontrollable mode of the linearization at $(z, x, \mu) = (0, 0, 0)$. If it is not zero, the normal form of the linear part is given by (8). If $\lambda = 0$ and if μ is considered as a state variable with $\dot{\mu} = 0$, the matrix of uncontrollable dynamic system is a zero matrix or it can be simplified into a Jordan block. This two cases are shown in (9) and (10).

The following quadratic transformations are employed to simplify the quadratic part of a system into its normal form while leaving the linear part invariant.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{z} \\ \bar{x} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} z \\ x \end{bmatrix} + \phi^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{u} = u + \alpha^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + \beta^{[1]}(z, x, \mu)u.$$

The normal forms are given in the following theorem. The notation $\tilde{f}^{[2]}(x)$ in the theorem represents the extended controller form obtained in [7].

Theorem 1 *Consider a control system satisfying assumption (3). Suppose that its linearization is in the form given by (8)-(10). Then, there exists a quadratic change of coordinates and feedback (11) which transforms the*

quadratic part of the system into one of the following normal forms.

(i) *For (8), the normal form is*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \lambda z + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} x_i^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \delta_\mu x_1 \mu + \gamma_{z\mu} z \mu + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(x) + \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

(ii) *For (9) the normal form is*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} x_i^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \delta_\mu x_1 \mu + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(x) + \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

(iii) *For (10), the normal form is*

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} x_i^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \delta_\mu x_1 \mu + \\ &\quad + \gamma_{z\mu} z \mu + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + \gamma_{\mu\mu} \mu^2 + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(x) + \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Proof. The theorem shows three quadratic normal forms for systems with different linearizations. We prove them separately.

(i) Suppose the linearization has the same form as (8). We consider the extended system consists of (8) and another equation $\dot{\mu} = 0$, i.e. μ is treated as a state variable. By the result in [8], there exists a quadratic transformation

$$\begin{aligned} z &= \bar{z} + \phi_1^{[2]}(\bar{z}, \bar{x}, \bar{\mu}), & x &= \bar{x} + \phi_2^{[2]}(\bar{z}, \bar{x}, \bar{\mu}), \\ \mu &= \bar{\mu} + \phi_3^{[2]}(\bar{z}, \bar{x}, \bar{\mu}), & u &= \bar{u} + \alpha^{[2]}(\bar{z}, \bar{x}, \bar{\mu}) + \beta(\bar{z}, \bar{x}, \bar{\mu})\bar{u} \end{aligned}$$

so that, under the new coordinates, the dynamics of \bar{z} and \bar{x} are in their quadratic normal forms given in [8], which are

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{z}} &= \lambda \bar{z} + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} \bar{x}_i^2 + \delta_z \bar{z} \bar{x}_1 + \delta_\mu \bar{x}_1 \bar{\mu} + \gamma_{z\mu} \bar{z} \bar{\mu} + \dots \\ \dot{\bar{x}} &= A \bar{x} + B \bar{u} + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(\bar{x}) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Since transformation (11) does not change the last variable μ , we substitute the relation $\mu = \bar{\mu} + \phi_3^{[2]}(\bar{z}, \bar{x}, \bar{\mu})$ back into (15). It is obvious that this will not change the linear and quadratic parts in the dynamics of \bar{z} and \bar{x} . Notice that the system (15) is in the same form as (12).

(ii) If a system has the same linearization as (9), the results in [8] do not provide a complete normal form for the system since the linearization of the uncontrollable part (including the dynamics of z and μ) is not diagonal. To simplify the proof by using the results in [8], let's first assume that $\mu = 0$. Then, system (9) can be transformed into the following normal form given in [8].

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} x_i^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + O(z, x, u)^3 \\ \dot{x} &= A_2 x + B_2 u + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(x) + O(z, x, u)^3. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the system with μ has the following form

$$\dot{z} = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} x_i^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + \gamma_{z\mu} z \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} b_{x_i\mu} x_i \mu + \gamma_{\mu\mu} \mu^2 + b_{\mu u} \mu u + \dots \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{x} = A_2 x + B_2 u + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(x) + d_{z\mu} z \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} d_{x_i\mu} x_i \mu + d_{\mu\mu} \mu^2 + d_{\mu u} \mu u + \dots$$

where $d_{z\mu}$, $d_{x_i\mu}$, $d_{\mu\mu}$ and $d_{\mu u}$ are constant vectors of dimension $n-1$. By a transformation

$$\bar{z} = z - b_{\mu u} \mu x_{n-1}, \quad \bar{x} = x - d_{\mu u} \mu x_{n-1}$$

the quadratic part μu in (16) can be cancelled. So, we focus on the system (16) in which $b_{\mu u} = d_{\mu u} = 0$. Let's consider a transformation

$$\bar{z} = z, \quad \bar{x} = x + \phi^{[2]}(z, x, \mu), \quad \bar{u} = u + \alpha^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + \beta^{[1]}(z, x, \mu) u \quad (17)$$

where $\phi^{[2]}(z, x, 0) = 0$ and $\alpha^{[2]}(z, x, 0) = 0$. To leave B_2 invariant, we also assume

$$\frac{\partial \phi_i^{[2]}}{\partial x_{n-1}} = 0 \quad (18)$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq n-2$, where $\phi_i^{[2]}$ is the i -th component of $\phi^{[2]}$. By the separation principle in [8], this transformation will not change the quadratic part of the uncontrollable dynamic system (the equation of z), it will not change the normal form $\tilde{f}^{[2]}$. Only the quadratic part related to μ in the controllable dynamic system is affected by this transformation. Denote $f_\mu(z, x, \mu)$ the quadratic terms with μ in the dynamics of x in (16)

$$f_\mu(z, x, \mu) = d_{z\mu} z \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} d_{x_i\mu} x_i \mu + d_{\mu\mu} \mu^2. \quad (19)$$

Similarly, if the transformation (17) is applied to (16), the quadratic terms with μ in the resulting dynamics of \bar{x} is denoted by $\bar{f}_\mu(z, x, \mu)$. The relation between f_μ and \bar{f}_μ is defined by the following homological equation from [8]

$$\bar{f}_\mu + \Pi(\phi^{[2]}, \alpha^{[2]}) = f_\mu, \quad (20)$$

where Π is the linear operator

$$\Pi(\phi^{[2]}, \alpha^{[2]}) = \frac{\partial \phi^{[2]}}{\partial x} A_2 x + \frac{\partial \phi^{[2]}}{\partial z} \mu - A_2 \phi^{[2]} - B_2 \alpha^{[2]}.$$

Define a linear space W to be the space consisting of quadratic vectors f_μ in the form of (19). Define V to be a linear space consisting of the elements $(\phi^{[2]}, \alpha^{[2]})$ satisfying (18). Then, Π is a linear map from V to W .

The pair $(\phi^{[2]}, \alpha^{[2]})$ is in the kernel of Π if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1^{[2]} &= a_1 z \mu + a_2 x_1 \mu + a_3 \mu^2, \\ \phi_i^{[2]} &= \frac{\partial \phi_{i-1}^{[2]}}{\partial x} A_2 x + \frac{\partial \phi_{i-1}^{[2]}}{\partial z} \mu, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n-1, \\ \alpha^{[2]} &= \frac{\partial \phi_{n-1}^{[2]}}{\partial x} A_2 x + \frac{\partial \phi_{n-1}^{[2]}}{\partial z} \mu \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the dimension of $\ker(\Pi)$ is 3. The dimension of the image space under Π is

$$\dim(\Pi(V)) = \dim(V) - \dim(\ker(\Pi)) = n^2 - 1 = \dim(W).$$

This implies that the map Π is onto. So, there exists a transformation given by $(\phi^{[2]}, \alpha^{[2]})$ in V which solves the homological equation (20) for $\bar{f}_\mu = 0$. Therefore, the vector field f_μ can be cancelled. By the homological equations of $g^{[1]}$ in [8] and the condition (18), a suitable choice of $\beta(z, x, \mu)$ will avoid the quadratic terms involving u . Therefore, the system can be simplified into the following form without f_μ

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z} &= \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} x_i^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + \gamma_{z\mu} z \mu + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} b_{x_i\mu} x_i \mu + \gamma_{\mu\mu} \mu^2 + \dots \\ \dot{x} &= Ax + Bu + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(x) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

In the system, all quadratic parts are in normal forms except the terms with μ in the equation of z . This part can be simplified by

$$\bar{z} = z + \sum_{i=1}^{n-2} c_{x_i\mu} x_i \mu + c_{z\mu} z \mu + c_{\mu\mu} \mu^2 + c_{zz} z^2. \quad (22)$$

From the separation principle in [8], this transformation does not change the terms in the controllable part. If the coefficients are $b_{x_i\mu} = -c_{x_{i-1}\mu}$ for $2 \leq i \leq n-1$, $\gamma_{\mu\mu} = -c_{z\mu}$ and $\gamma_{z\mu} = -2c_{zz}$, the quadratic part of system (21) can be simplified into the normal form (13).

(iii) The argument similar to the proof of (i) can be applied to (iii). Given a system (10). If μ is considered as a state variable, the extended system can be simplified into a normal form ([8])

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{z}} &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \delta_{n-i} \bar{x}_i^2 + \delta_z \bar{z} \bar{x}_1 + \delta_\mu \bar{x}_1 \bar{\mu} \\ &\quad + \gamma_{z\mu} \bar{z} \bar{\mu} + \gamma_{zz} \bar{z}^2 + \gamma_{\mu\mu} \bar{\mu}^2 + \dots \\ \dot{\bar{x}} &= A \bar{x} + B \bar{u} + \tilde{f}^{[2]}(\bar{x}) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The quadratic transformation is

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{z} &= z + \phi_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu), \quad \bar{x} = x + \phi_2^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) \\ \bar{\mu} &= \mu + \phi_3^{[2]}(z, x, \mu), \quad \bar{u} = u + \alpha^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) + \beta(z, x, \mu) u. \end{aligned}$$

Since the transformation for our purpose do not change μ , we substitute $\bar{\mu} = \mu + \phi_3^{[2]}(z, x, \mu)$ back into (23). It

is easy to see that this will not change the linear and quadratic parts of the dynamics of z and x . Notice that the system (23) is in the same form as (14). \triangleleft

In the following, it is shown that the normal form of a system is completely determined by the invariants. The computation of invariants is straightforward. Given a control system, the normal form can be found without finding the change of coordinates. For the reason of simplicity, we assume that the linearization of the system is in the form of (8)-(10). The parameter μ is treated as a state variable such that $\dot{\mu} = 0$. In the following, the *extended system* (including the original system and $\dot{\mu} = 0$) is denoted by

$$\dot{x}_e = f_e(x_e) + g_e(x_e)u. \quad (24)$$

If a system is in one of the forms given by (8)-(10), then the extended system (24) has state variables

$$x_e = [z \quad x \quad \mu]^T.$$

Denote C_z, C_x, X_z, X_μ the following row and column vectors in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}

$$\begin{aligned} C_z &= [1 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0] & C_x &= [0 \quad 1 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0] \\ X_z &= [1 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0]^T & X_\mu &= [0 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0 \quad 1]^T \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The linearization of the extended system at $z = 0, x = 0, \mu = 0$ is denoted by (A_e, B_e) ,

$$A_e = \left. \frac{\partial f_e}{\partial x_e} \right|_{z=0, x=0, \mu=0}, \quad B_e = g_e(0).$$

Definition 1 Given a control system satisfying (3). Suppose that its linearization is in the form of (8)-(10). The quadratic invariants are defined to be the following numbers, where all the Lie brackets are evaluated at the origin.

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{tr} &= \frac{1}{2} C_x A_e^{t-1} [ad_{f_e}^r(g_e), ad_{f_e}^{r-1}(g_e)], & 1 \leq r \leq n-3, & 1 \leq t \leq n-r-2 \\ \delta_r &= \frac{1}{2} C_z [ad_{f_e}^r(g_e), ad_{f_e}^{r-1}(g_e)], & 1 \leq r \leq n-1 \\ \delta_z &= (-1)^{n-1} C_z [X_z, ad_{f_e}^{n-1}(g_e)], \\ \delta_\mu &= (-1)^{n-1} C_z [X_\mu, ad_{f_e}^{n-1}(g_e)] \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

and for (12)

$$\gamma_{z\mu} = \text{the coefficient of } z\mu \text{ in } f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) \quad (27)$$

for (13)

$$\gamma_{zz} = \text{the coefficient of } z^2 \text{ in } f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) \quad (28)$$

for (14)

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{z\mu} &= \text{the coefficient of } z\mu \text{ in } f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) \\ \gamma_{zz} &= \text{the coefficient of } z^2 \text{ in } f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu) \\ \gamma_{\mu\mu} &= \text{the coefficient of } \mu^2 \text{ in } f_1^{[2]}(z, x, \mu). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Theorem 2 Given a system satisfying (3). Suppose its linearization is in the form of (8)-(10).

(i) Quadratic transformations defined by (11) do not change the values of the quadratic invariants.

(ii) The quadratic invariants of normal form (12)-(14) are the corresponding coefficients of the quadratic terms.

Proof. (i) The quadratic invariants $\lambda_{tr}, \delta_r, \delta_z$ and δ_μ are defined in the same way as the invariants for systems without parameters because the parameters in the system are treated as state variables. Similar to the proof in [10], it can be proved that $\lambda_{tr}, \delta_r, \delta_z$ and δ_μ are invariant under the quadratic change of coordinates and feedback (11). For systems in the form of (8), the term $z\mu$ is the resonant term in the dynamic system of (z, μ) and they can not be changed by change of coordinates of the form

$$\bar{z} = z + \phi^{[2]}(z, \mu).$$

By the separation principle in [8], the coefficient of a resonant term does not change under any quadratic transformation of the form (11). Similarly, one can prove that, for system (10), $\gamma_{zz}, \gamma_{z\mu}$ and $\gamma_{\mu\mu}$ are invariant under the quadratic transformations because they are resonant terms. If system (9) is under consideration, γ_{zz} is invariant under (22), this can be proved by calculation. By the separation principle in [8], transformations other than (22) do not change the coefficient γ_{zz} .

(ii) By the definition of invariants, it is obvious that

$$\gamma_{z\mu}, \gamma_{zz}, \gamma_{\mu\mu}$$

are the coefficients of $z\mu, z^2$ and μ^2 , respectively. For the other invariants, we will prove the result for system (13). The other two cases are similar. Keep in mind that the state variables are in the order of z, x, μ for the extended system. The Lie brackets of f_e and g_e are

$$\begin{aligned} ad_{f_e}^r(g_e) &= (-1)^r (X_{n-r} + \\ & [2\delta_r x_{n-r} \quad 2\lambda_{1r} x_{n-r} \quad \cdots \quad 2\lambda_{n-r-2r} x_{n-r} \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0]^T \\ & + h_r(x_{n-r+1}, x_{n-r+2}, \cdots, x_{n-1})) + O(z, x, \mu)^2 \end{aligned}$$

for $1 \leq r < n-2$, where X_i is a vector in which the i th entry is 1 and the rest are zeros. For $r = n-2$ and $r = n-1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} ad_{f_e}^{n-2}(g_e) &= (-1)^{n-2} (X_2 + [2\delta_{n-2} x_2 \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0]^T) \\ & + h_{n-2}(x_3, x_4, \cdots, x_{n-1}) + O(z, x, \mu)^2 \\ ad_{f_e}^{n-1}(g_e) &= (-1)^{n-1} [2\delta_{n-1} x_1 + \delta_z z + \delta_\mu \mu \quad 0 \quad \cdots \quad 0] \\ & + h_{n-1}(x_2, x_3, \cdots, x_{n-1}) + O(z, x, \mu)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting these relations into the right side of (26), they are equal to the corresponding coefficients. \triangleleft

Given a system satisfying assumption (3). The linear part of the system can be transformed into a system in one of the forms given by (8), (9) or (10). They have

different bifurcation patterns which are addressed in the following sections.

3. THE EQUILIBRIUM SET

In this section, parametrizations are given for the equilibrium set of systems satisfying assumption 3. Locally they are approximated by quadratic surfaces.

Theorem 3 Consider a system of form (8). The equilibrium set E satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= \nu \\ z &= O(\nu, \mu)^2 \\ x_i &= O(\nu, \mu)^2, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-1. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Remark. The theorem implies that the equilibrium set is a two dimensional manifold. At the origin, the manifold is tangent to the $x_1\mu$ -space. For any fixed μ_0 , the set of equilibrium points with $\mu = \mu_0$ is a smooth curve in the state space. Therefore, the equilibrium set does not have bifurcation. However, it can be proved that the controllability of the system changes as the equilibrium points are varied. The proof of this fact is omitted for the reason of space. \triangleleft

Proof. Given any quadratic change of coordinates and feedback (11). Under the new coordinates, the equations in (30) are equivalent to

$$\bar{x}_1 = \bar{\nu}, \quad \bar{z} = O(\bar{\nu}, \mu)^2, \quad x_i = O(\bar{\nu}, \mu)^2$$

which have the same form as (30). Therefore, the property of Theorem 3 is invariant under quadratic transformations. To prove the result, it is enough to show the result for systems in the normal form. Consider system (12), it is obvious that a point in the equilibrium set satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} x_i + O(z, x, \mu)^2 &= 0, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-1 \\ \lambda z + O(z, x, \mu)^2 &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

The solution of these equations for x_i , $i = 2, \dots, n-1$ and z is in the form of (30). \triangleleft

Now, we consider system (9). In this case, the values of x_1 and z are used as the parameters of the equilibrium set E . Furthermore, since transformation (11) does not change μ , all the quadratic terms in the parametric equation of μ can be found.

Theorem 4 Given a system (9). Its equilibrium set satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= \nu_1, \quad z = \nu_2 \\ \mu &= -\delta_{n-1}\nu_1^2 - \delta_z\nu_1\nu_2 - \gamma_{zz}\nu_2^2 + O(\nu_1, \nu_2)^3 \\ x_i &= O(\nu_1, \nu_2)^2 \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-1. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Remark. The projection of E to $zx_1\mu$ -space is approximately a quadratic surface. It is a paraboloid or a saddle. In fact, if the matrix

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \delta & \frac{\delta_z}{2} \\ \frac{\delta_z}{2} & \gamma_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

is sign definite ($\det(Q) > 0$), E is approximately a paraboloid. If (32) is not sign definite but it has full rank ($\det(Q) < 0$), E is approximately a saddle. In any case, E has bifurcation near $\mu = 0$. More specifically, we define

$$E_{\mu_0} = \{(x, \mu) | (x, \mu) \in E\} \quad (33)$$

Then the topology of E_μ changes as μ passing through zero. If E is approximately a paraboloid, E_μ is empty for the values of μ on one side of zero and it is a closed curve for μ on the other side. If E is approximately a saddle, then E_μ is approximately two lines meet at the origin for $\mu = 0$. It is a connected set. However, E_μ is approximately a hyperbola for $\mu \neq 0$ which is not a connect set. \triangleleft

Proof. Modulo the higher degree terms in (31), ($O(\nu_1, \nu_2)^3$ in the equation of μ and $O(\nu_1, \mu_2)^2$ in the equations of x_i , $i = 2, \dots, n-1$), the functions are invariant under transformation (11). Therefore, we only consider a system in normal form, which is (13). Any point in the equilibrium set satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &= O(x_1, \mu)^2, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-1 \\ u &= O(x_1, \mu)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Substituting this relation into the right side of the system and setting it to be zero, we have

$$\mu + \delta_{n-1}x_1 + \delta_z z x_1 + \delta_\mu x_1 \mu + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + O(z, x_1, \mu)^3 = 0.$$

Define $x_1 = \nu_1$ and $z = \nu_2$. The equation has a unique solution for μ near $\mu = 0$ and its solution is in the form of (31). \triangleleft

To find a parametrization for the set E of (10), the matrix of the quadratic part in the uncontrollable dynamics is very important. This matrix for normal form (14) in terms of invariants is

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{zz} & \frac{1}{2}\delta_z & \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{z\mu} \\ \frac{1}{2}\delta_z & \delta_{n-1} & \frac{1}{2}\delta_\mu \\ \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{z\mu} & \frac{1}{2}\delta_\mu & \gamma_{\mu\mu} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (35)$$

The eigenvalues of Q are denoted by $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$. Suppose T_1, T_2, T_3 are three column unit eigenvectors of Q associated with the eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$, respectively. In the parametrization of E , new variables w_1, w_2, w_3 are used. Their relation with the state variables and parameters are

$$[w_1 \quad w_2 \quad w_3]^T = [T_1 \quad T_2 \quad T_3]^T \begin{bmatrix} z \\ x_1 \\ \mu \end{bmatrix}. \quad (36)$$

Theorem 5 Given a system satisfying (3). Suppose its linearization is in the form of (10).

(i) If Q is positive definite or negative definite, then $(z, x, \nu) = (0, 0, 0)$ is an isolated equilibrium point.

(ii) If Q is not sign definite and if it has full rank, then the equilibrium set satisfies

$$w_3 = \pm \sqrt{-\frac{\lambda_1 w_1^2 + \lambda_2 w_2^2}{\lambda_3}} + O(w_1, w_2)^2 \quad (37)$$

$$x_i = O(w_1, w_2)^2, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-1$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 represent the two eigenvalues with the same sign and w_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$, is defined by (36).

Remark. In case (ii), the graph of the equilibrium set in $zx\mu$ -plane is approximated by a cone

$$\lambda_1 w_1^2 + \lambda_2 w_2^2 + \lambda_3 w_3^2 = 0.$$

The center line of the cone is parallel to the eigenvectors of λ_3 . For any fixed value of μ , the set of equilibrium points E_μ (defined in (33)) is approximately a conic curve. The shape of E_μ depends on the orientation of the cone in $zx_1\mu$ -space. Furthermore, for small values of μ , the topology of E_μ at $\mu = 0$ is always different from that of E_μ at $\mu \neq 0$. \triangleleft

Proof. (i) Consider the system (14). The points in equilibrium set satisfy equation (34). Substituting (34) into the right side of the dynamics and setting it to be zero, we have

$$\delta_{n-1}x_1^2 + \delta_z z x_1 + \delta_\mu x_1 \mu + \gamma_{z\mu} z \mu + \gamma_{zz} z^2 + \gamma_{\mu\mu} \mu^2 + \dots = 0. \quad (38)$$

The matrix of the quadratic function in (38) is given by (35). Therefore, if the matrix Q is positive definite or negative definite, so is the function on the left side of (38). It has no nontrivial solution near $(z, x_1, \mu) = (0, 0, 0)$.

(ii) If the matrix Q in (35) is not sign definite, and if it has full rank, then the matrix has three nonzero eigenvalues λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 . Furthermore, we can assume that $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 > 0$. Then λ_3 has different sign from λ_1 and λ_2 . By a change of coordinates (36), the equation (38) becomes

$$\lambda_1 w_1^2 + \lambda_2 w_2^2 + \lambda_3 w_3^2 + O(w_1, w_2, w_3)^3 = 0.$$

Solving the equation for w_3 . The solution is in the form of (37). \triangleleft

4. CONCLUSION

For control systems satisfying assumption (3), their equilibrium sets are classified under changes of coordinates and feedbacks.

Another relevant topic is the relations between quadratic invariants and controllability or stabilizability. This is addressed in another paper. In general, the uncontrollable equilibrium points form a one dimensional curve. The tangent line of the curve is uniquely determined by quadratic invariants. If E is a paraboloid or a saddle, then it is proved that the stabilizability changes as an uncontrollable equilibrium point passing through the origin.

Our recent research shows that the closed loop system under state feedbacks can have transcritical, saddle-node or pitchfork bifurcations. The stability properties of the closed-loop system bifurcation can be determined by the invariants and normal forms.

References

- [1] E. Abed and J-H Fu, *Local feedback stabilization and bifurcation control, I. Hopf bifurcation*, Systems and Control Letters, 7, pp11-17, 1986.
- [2] E. Abed and J-H Fu, *Local feedback stabilization and bifurcation control, II. Stationary bifurcation.*, Systems and Control Letters, 8, pp467-473, 1987
- [3] A. Abichou and B. d'Andria-Novel, *Smooth stabilizing feedback for a class of mechanical systems with a pitchfork bifurcation*, Systems and Control Letters, 22, pp393-405, 1994.
- [4] V. I. Arnold, *Geometrical Methods in the Theory of Ordinary Differential Equations*, second edition, Springer-Verlag, 1988.
- [5] F. Colonius and W. Kliemann, *Controllability and stabilization of one-dimensional systems near bifurcation points*, Systems and Control Letters, vol. 24, pp87-95, 1995.
- [6] J. Hale and H. Kocak, *Dynamics and Bifurcations*, Springer-Verlag, 1991.
- [7] W. Kang and A. J. Krener, *Extended quadratic controller normal form and dynamic feedback linearization of nonlinear systems*, SIAM J. Control and Optimization, vol. 30, No. 6, pp 1319-1337, 1992.
- [8] W. Kang, *Quadratic normal forms of nonlinear control systems with uncontrollable linearization*, Proc. IEEE Conf. on Decision and Control, 1995.
- [9] W. Kang, *Extended controller form and invariants of nonlinear control systems with a single input*, J. of Mathematical System, Estimation and Control, vol. 4, No. 2, 1994, pp253-256.
- [10] W. Kang, *Bifurcation and normal form of nonlinear control systems - Part I*, submitted to SIAM J. Control and Optimization.
- [11] S. Wiggins, *Introduction to Applied Nonlinear Dynamical Systems and Chaos*, Springer-Verlag, 1990.